

report the characterization of several compounds isolated from the leaves of this plant.

Experimental

The air dried powdered leaves of *A. indica* were extracted exhaustively in turn with petroleum ether (60–80°), benzene and chloroform and finally percolated with ethanol.

The petroleum ether (60–80°) concentrate was subjected to column chromatography over Brockmann alumina. Elution of the column with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (3:1) mixture yielded a solid m.p. 65–67°, identified as *n*-hentriacontane³ by comparison (m.m.p. co-tlc and superimposable ir spectra) with authentic sample

Further elution of the column with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (1:1) mixture afforded colourless crystals, m.p. 84–85°. It did not give any colour reaction for triterpene or sterol and was characterised as *n*-hentriacontanol⁴ from mass spectral data, m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir with authentic specimen.

Fraction eluted with petroleum ether (60–80°)-benzene (1:3) yielded a sterol, m.p. 135–36°, acetate, m.p. 126°, identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-ir) with authentic sample. Further elution of the column with the same solvent furnished a white solid crystallised from acetone, m.p. 79–81°, oxime, m.p. 56–58°. Super imposable ir spectra, co-tlc and m.m.p. established its identity as palmitone.

The benzene, chloroform and alcoholic extracts on similar chromatographic resolution afforded only β -sitosterol.

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References

1. R. N. CHOPRA, S. L. NAYAR and I. C. CHOPRA, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants", CSIR, Delhi, (India), 1956, p. 8.
2. "The Wealth of India (Raw Materials)", CSIR, Delhi (India), 1948, Vol. I, p. 35.
3. I. HEILBORN and H. M. BUNBURY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", London: Eyre and Spottiswoode Publishers Ltd., 1965 Vol. 3, p. 1566.
4. I. HEILBORN and H. M. BUNBURY, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds", London: Eyre and Spottiswoode Publishers Ltd., 1965, Vol. 3, p. 1957.

Studies on the Genus Piper—IX: Characterization of Abnormal Products*: Synthesis of Dihydro and Tetrahydropiperlongumic Acid

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DURING the course of our reinvestigation on the structure of the alkaloid piperlongumine (piperlongumine)^{1,2} we tried to verify the structure of the tetrahydro derivative by a synthesis which involves the condensation of 3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamoyl chloride with α -piperidone in presence of pyridine followed by simple reduction of the condensation product, dihydropiperlongumine. But the condensation reaction furnished the anhydride of 3,4,5-trimethoxy cinnamic acid⁽¹⁾ C₂₄H₂₆O₉ (M⁺458), m.p. 185–86°, ir absorption for anhydride function (1724 and 1574 cm⁻¹) and a minor constituent, compound-A, instead of the desired product dihydropiperlongumine.

The minor constituent, compound A, C₁₇H₂₃NO₆ (M⁺337) exhibits ir absorption bands at 3333 cm⁻¹ (NH and/or OH), 1689 cm⁻¹ (C=O of a nonconjugated -COOH), 1653 cm⁻¹ (monosubstituted α,β -unsaturated carboxamide) and 990 cm⁻¹ (*trans*-CH=CH-). PMR spectrum of the compound **I**A, studied in CDCl₃, shows a pair of doublets around δ 6.30 and 7.60 (J=16 Hz) attributed to the α - and β -protons of a styryl nucleus whereas the singlets at δ 6.73 (2H) and δ 3.90 (9H) confirm the presence of 1-substituted 3,4,5-trimethoxybenzene chromophore in the molecule. A two proton multiplet around δ 3.80 indicates the presence of a methylene group adjacent to nitrogen atom. Two other multiplets around δ 2.67 and δ 1.47 may be assigned to the remaining six methylene protons present in the molecule.

The presence of the 3,4,5-trimethoxycinnamoyl moiety is also confirmed by the formation of the base peak at m/e 221 from the molecular ion (M⁺337) in the mass spectrum of the compound. The other significant fragment at m/e 19 arises by the loss of water involving -COOH group and a δ -hydrogen through a six membered transition state³.

All these spectral and chemical data can readily be explained on the basis of structure (II) for the compound A. This structure (II) is further confirmed by

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its conversion to tetrahydropiperlongumic acid¹, $C_{17}H_{25}NO_6$, m.p. 114° by catalytic hydrogenation.

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References

1. A. CHATTERJEE and C. P. DUTTA, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 23, 1769.
2. B. S. JOSHI, V. N. KAMAT and A. K. SAKSENA, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, 2395.
3. S. MEYERSON and L. C. LEITCH, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 88, 56.
4. R. JOLY, R. BUCOURT and E. TOROMANLOFF, *Chem. Abs.*, 1960, 54, 14292; US Pat 2, 926, 167 (1960).

Studies on Heterocyclic Compounds : Part I.

Synthesis of 3-amino-2-sub-Imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridines

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BRISTOW *et al*¹ prepared 2-pyridyl amino acetonitrile in search for antihistaminic properties and suggested that the compounds behaved as amines by rearrangement rather than as nitriles. Ohta *et al*² also

prepared the α -(2-pyridyl amino)-sub acetonitriles and used them for the preparation of mesoionic compounds. Almirante *et al*³ also synthesised nitrogen containing derivatives of imidazo(1,2-1)-pyridine for the study of their pharmacological properties.

In continuation of our studies on ($\pm$)-aminoacetonitriles⁴, we have prepared ($\pm$)-pyridyl aminoacetonitriles which rearrange into 3-amino-2-imidazo(1,2-a)-pyridines. The aldehyde bisulphite addition product

3-Amino-2-sub-imidazo (1,2-a)-pyridines

was reacted with 2-aminopyridine followed by aqueous potassium cyanide to get the imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridines (Table 1). The ir spectrum of 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1,2-a)-pyridine supported the amine structure confirming the view of Bristow *et al*^(1, 2). Another supporting evidence has been obtained by condensing 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridine with different aldehydes when anils were obtained (Table 2).

The ir spectrum of 3-amino-2-phenyl-imidazo (1, 2-a)-pyridine recorded on Backman IR 5 spectrophotometer on KBr pellet shows characteristic aminofrequencies instead of any absorption between 2260-2240 cm^{-1} (the $-C\equiv N$ -region). Most of the compounds showed antibacterial activity in preliminary screening.

TABLE 1

3-AMINO-2-SUB-IMIDAZO (1, 2-A)-PYRIDINES

No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	% N	
				Found	Required
1.	H	C_7H_7N	124	31.70	31.57
2.	CH_3	C_8H_9N	134	28.67	28.57
3.	C_6H_5	$C_{12}H_{11}N$	210	20.20	20.09
4.	2-Cl- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{10}ClN$	152	17.42	17.24
5.	2-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{11}N_2O$	122	18.42	18.66
6.	2-OH-5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{12}H_{10}BrN_2O$	220	13.61	13.81
7.	4-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{12}H_{11}N_2O$	210 (d)	16.72	16.66
8.	C_6H_5O	$C_{11}H_9N_2O$	175 (d)	20.20	21.11
9.	4- CH_3O - C_6H_4	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2O$	131	17.47	17.57
10.	4-OH-3- OCH_3 - C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2O_2$	222	16.32	16.47
11.	2- OCH_3 -5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{12}BrN_2O$	210	13.42	13.20
12.	3,4- CH_2O_2 - C_6H_3	$C_{14}H_{11}N_2O_2$	255 (d)	16.82	16.60
13.	4- $CH_3C_6H_4$	$C_{14}H_{13}N_2$	252	18.92	18.83

TABLE 2

3-ARYLIDINE AMINO-2-PHENYL-IMIDAZO (1, 2-A)-PYRIDINES

No.	R	Molecular formula	m.p. °C	% N	
				Found	Required
1.	C_6H_5	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3$	137	14.20	14.14
2.	2-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3O$	245	13.60	13.41
3.	4-OH- C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{15}N_3O$	160	13.23	13.41
4.	2-OH-5-Br- C_6H_3	$C_{20}H_{14}BrN_3O$	182	10.62	10.71
5.	4- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2$	205	16.52	16.37
6.	3- NO_2 - C_6H_4	$C_{20}H_{14}N_4O_2$	149	16.10	16.37
7.	C_6H_5O	$C_{18}H_{13}N_3O$	139	14.82	14.63
8.	4-OH-3- CH_3O - C_6H_3	$C_{21}H_{17}N_3O_2$	208	12.12	12.24